
EVALUATING THE RIGHT TO EQUALITY THROUGH THE LENS OF LEGAL JURISPRUDENCE AND EFFICIENCY CONSIDERATIONS

Kenekayoro T. Peter

Lecturer, Faculty of Law, University of Africa, Toru-Orua, Bayelsa State, Nigeria.

E-mail: Kenekayoroxoxo@gmail.com

Phone Number: 08054813928

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17043970>

Abstract: This study involves a legal evaluation of the right to equality. Legislative and treaty provisions that support and recognize the right to equality are referenced to verify the legal value of the right, including the African Charter on Human and Peoples' Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act (ACHPR), Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR), International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights (ICCPR), and International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR). This research evaluates the right to equality from different dimensions, for example, from the point of view of substantive equality or equality before the law, distributive equality as recognized by Articles 19 and 22 of the ACHPR; the creation of institutionalized standards of equality by virtue of public policies or administrative decisions; and the specification of qualification-based standards of equality that are predicated on efficiency considerations, i.e., quality-based requirements. This research also alludes to various challenges undermining the right to equality, which can be political, administrative, or economic or resource-based limitations. In conclusion, this research reiterates the fact that equality standards are recognized by law, and efficiency considerations can be the basis of its conditionalization, in view of professional or technical qualifications. However, due to existing inefficiencies, inefficacies, and systemic flaws, various economic, administrative, and political factors undermine the right to equality, especially in systemically corrupt countries.

Keywords: Rights, equality, qualification, law, efficiency

1. Introduction

Many written constitutions contain express statements guaranteeing the right to equality [...] English courts in applying the Common Law have taken the view that unequal treatment that cannot be justified may constitute an irrational act by a public authority [...] The existence of a 'right to equality', however defined, is now therefore often regarded as an essential feature of both national law and international human rights instruments.¹

There are various legal and jurisprudential references to equality, for example the equal right of all persons 'to a fair and public hearing by an independent and impartial tribunal, in the determination of rights and obligations';²

¹ C O'Conneide, 'the Right to Equality: A Substantive Legal Norm or Vacuous Rhetoric?' [2008] *UCL Human Rights Review*, 81.

² Article 4 of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, adopted and proclaimed by resolution 217 A (III) of the General Assembly on December 10, 1948;

the duty of States to ‘take appropriate steps to ensure equality of rights’³; equal access to the public service of the country;⁴ the maintenance of an order based on the principles of ‘equal rights and self-determination of peoples, justice, equality, and the rule of law’;⁵ freedom from discrimination and equality before the law;⁶ gender equality;⁷ ‘collective responsibility to uphold the principles of equality and equity at the global level’;⁸ ‘respect for all human rights and fundamental freedoms of indigenous people, on the basis of equality and non-discrimination, and recognizing the value and diversity of their distinct identities, cultures and social organization’;⁹ ‘sovereign equality of all States, respect for their territorial integrity and political independence’;¹⁰ equality of educational opportunity;¹¹ equality of opportunity or treatment in employment or occupation;¹² racial and ethnic equality;¹³ equal access to ‘faculties for attaining the highest level in intellectual, technical, social, economic, cultural and political development’;¹⁴ equal right to practice religion;¹⁵ ‘the right to equal remuneration, including benefits, and to equal treatment in respect of work of equal value, as well as equality of treatment in the evaluation of the quality of work’;¹⁶ and ‘the immediate and final elimination of all forms of inequality, exploitation of peoples and individuals, colonialism and racism, including Nazism and apartheid, and all other policies and ideologies opposed to the purposes and principles of the United Nations.’¹⁷ The right to equality can be evaluated from different dimensions, such as the doctrinal principle of substantive equality and the rule of law, distributive

Article 14(3) of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, adopted and opened for signature, ratification, and accession by the General Assembly resolution 2200 A (XXI) of December 16, 1966

³ Article 23(4) of the ICCPR

⁴ Ibid Article 25(c)

⁵ Preamble of the Vienna Declaration and Program of Action (VDPA) adopted by the World Conference on Human Rights in Vienna on June 25, 1993

⁶ ibid Part I, Article 19

Preamble of the Basic Principles on the Independence of the Judiciary, adopted by the Seventh United Nations Congress on the Prevention of Crime and the Treatment of Offenders held in Milan from August 26, 1985, to September 6, 1985, and endorsed by General Assembly resolutions 40/32 of 29 November 1985 and 40/146 of December 13, 1985

⁷ ‘n 5’ Part 3, Article 40

⁸ Part I (Values and Principles) Article 2 of the United Nations Millennium Declaration General Assembly resolution 55/2 of September 8, 2000 (UNMD)

⁹ ‘n 5’ Part I, Article 20

¹⁰ ‘n 8’ Part I, Article 4

¹¹ Preamble of the Convention against Discrimination in Education, adopted by the General Conference of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization on December 14, 1960

¹² Article 1 of the Discrimination (Employment and Occupation) Convention, 1958 (No. 111) was adopted on June 25, 1958, by the General Conference of the International Labor Organization at its forty-second session.

¹³ Article 4(1) of the Declaration on Race and Racial Prejudice, adopted and proclaimed by the General Conference of the United Nations Educational, Scientific, and Cultural Organization at its 20th session, on November 27, 1978

¹⁴ Ibid Article 1(4)

¹⁵ Preamble of the Declaration on the Elimination of All Forms of Intolerance and of Discrimination Based on Religion or Belief Proclaimed by General Assembly resolution 36/55 of November 25, 1981

¹⁶ Article 11(1) (d) of the Convention on the Elimination of All Forms of Discrimination against Women, adopted and opened for signature, ratification, and accession by the General Assembly resolution 34/180 of December 18, 1979

¹⁷ Article 2(a) of the Declaration on Social Progress and Development, proclaimed by resolution 2542 (XXIV) of the General Assembly of December 11, 1969

equality with regard to economic resources, or conditional equality based on stipulated qualification standards or efficiency considerations.

2. Substantive equality or equality before the law

The principle of equality before the law is centered on the rule of law, and its universal and non-discriminatory applicability.¹⁸ States are entrusted with the task of guaranteeing all citizens' right to equal protection by the law. On the contrary, there are various instances in which the actions of states have been deemed prejudicial or contrary to the principle of equality. For example, the case of *Josef Frank Adam v. The Czech Republic*,¹⁹ involved Article 26 of the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, which provides the following:

The law shall prohibit any discrimination and guarantee to all persons equal and effective protection against discrimination on any ground, such as race, color, sex, language, religion, political or other opinion, national or social origin, property, birth or other status.

The author's father, Vlatislav Adam, was a Czech citizen. The Czechoslovak Government, confiscated his property and business in 1949. However, as a result of the democratization process initiated by the government of the Czech and Slovak Republic in 1989, a considerable effort was made "to remove some of the property injustices caused by the communist regime."²⁰ For instance, in 1949, Vlatislav's company and, all properties on the premises were confiscated by the state, a situation that caused him to immigrate illegally to West Germany, where he lived as a refugee for one year.²¹ Before Vlatislav Adam's death in 1985, by virtue of his last will and testament, he left his property in Czechoslovakia to his sons. Nonetheless, all the beneficiaries' efforts to reclaim their father's property from the State were futile.²²

In 1991, the Czech and Slovak Republic enacted a law for the rehabilitation of Czech citizens who migrated due to communist pressure. The law aimed at restitution of properties and compensation for losses. In 1991, the author submitted a claim for the restitution of the family property. However, the claim was denied on the basis of the preconditions stipulated by Act 87/91, which requires applicants to possess Czech citizenship and permanent residence in the Czech Republic.²³ The petitions of the author were all rejected based on the justification that the dual requirement of citizenship and permanent residence was, a necessary legislative measure that applies 'uniformly to all claimants'. Therefore, the claimants were of the view that the State's denial of their legitimate right to inheritance amounts to a violation of Article 26 of the Covenant, considering the position of the Czechoslovak law and the fact that their father was a property owner and a Czech citizen.²⁴ Thus, in a letter

¹⁸ The rule of law is centered on the supremacy of the law and its applicability, to all, irrespective of social, economic, or political status. K Peter, Violation of the Rule of Law and Abuse of Public Authority: as Factors Procuring the Breach of the Right to Life, *Int. J. Adv. Res.*, vol. 13, no. 5, 2025, p. 272

¹⁹ CCPR/C/57/D/586/1994

²⁰ *Josef Frank Adam v. Czech Republic* CCPR/C/57/D/586/1994 para 9.1, 10.1

²¹ *ibid*

²² 'n 20' paras 2.1, 2.2, 2.3, and 10.2

²³ *ibid*

²⁴ *ibid*

submitted on November 7, 1994, the author informed the Human Rights Committee (HRC) that “the State party is trying to circumvent his rights by placing his property and business on sale.”²⁵

The Czech Constitutional Law, including the Charter of Fundamental Rights and Freedoms, guarantees inheritance and protects the right to own property.²⁶ However, expropriation is legally guaranteed, solely based on the justification of public interest, and is subject to compensation.²⁷ On that account, the State considered the imposition of conditions limiting property rights based on citizenship as legitimate.²⁸ Nevertheless, the circumstances of the case raises questions regarding, the legitimacy of the conditions imposed by the state for the recovery of confiscated properties. Therefore, the core issue for determination “is whether the application of Act 87/1991 to the author and his brothers entailed a violation of their right to equality before the law and to equal protection of the law.”²⁹ After considering the facts, the Human Rights Committee held the State liable for a violation of Article 26 of the ICCPR, based on the following view:

Such legislation must not discriminate among the victims of the prior confiscations because, all victims are entitled to redress without arbitrary distinctions.³⁰ Considering that the State party itself is responsible for the departure of the author’s parents in 1949, requiring him and his brothers to obtain Czech citizenship as a prerequisite for the restitution of their property or, for the payment of appropriate compensation would be incompatible with the Covenant.³¹ Thus, pursuant to Article 2 of the Covenant, the State party has undertaken to ensure the rights recognized in the Covenant are granted to all individuals within its territory and subject to its jurisdiction and to provide an effective and enforceable remedy in case a violation has been established.³²

However, Nisuke Ando inter-alia stated, that ‘under current rules of general international law, States are free to choose their economic system’ and that ‘while the ICCPR enshrines the principle of non-discrimination and equality before the law, it does not prohibit “legitimate distinctions” based on objective and reasonable criteria’.³³ The aforementioned opinion points out the qualification standard that laws must be reason-centric orders/declarations, which is consistent with Cicero’s jurisprudential conceptualization of law,³⁴ the public order doctrine, and the justification of legitimate objectives.³⁵ Consequently, laws must not be based on discriminatory

²⁵ *Josef Frank Adam v. Czech Republic* CCPR/C/57/D/586/1994 para 5.1, 5.2

²⁶ Articles 1 and 3 of the Charter stipulate equality in the enjoyment of rights and prohibit discrimination.

‘n 25’ paras 8.6 and 8.8

²⁷ ‘n 25’ para 8.6

²⁸ *Josef Frank Adam v. Czech Republic* CCPR/C/57/D/586/1994 para 9.3

²⁹ *ibid* para 12.3

³⁰ *ibid* para 12.5

³¹ *ibid* para 12.6

³² *ibid* para 13.3

³³ Individual opinion by Mr. Nisuke Ando on Communication No. 586/1994 (*Adam v. Czech Republic*), in line with Rule 94, Paragraph 3, of the Rules of Procedure of the Human Rights Committee

³⁴ P Gasiokwu, ‘State, Law and the Challenges of Good Governance: Law, Politics and Diplomacy in Contemporary Nigeria’ [2010] 25

<<https://www.researchgate.net/publication/342277563>> accessed 21 April 2025

³⁵ Article 29 (2) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights

Adopted and proclaimed by the General Assembly resolution 217 A (III) of December 10, 1948

or unjustifiable standards, which are likely to procure a miscarriage of justice.³⁶ In a general sense, all persons are entitled to the state's equal protection and recognition of their rights and interests. The rule of law is supreme and, equally applicable to all persons based on neutral and objective criteria and qualifications consistent with justice.³⁷

The case of *José Luis García Fuenzalida v Ecuador*,³⁸ involved a Chilean citizen who, resided in Quito, Ecuador. At the time of submission of the communication, he was imprisoned at Cárcel No. 2 in Quito.³⁹ The author's claims against Ecuador are based on violations of Articles 3, 7, 9, and 14 of the International Covenant on Civil Rights. He was allegedly arrested without a warrant or information of the charges against him; subjected to inhumane and degrading treatment; tortured and coerced to sign an incriminatory statement; 'in contravention of Ecuadorian law and practice, samples of his blood and hair were taken';⁴⁰ and his case was neglected by state authorities, based on the failure to determine the appeal within the statutorily mandated timeframe, 'after more than two and a half years of waiting for the decision of the Court of Cassation'.⁴¹ After due consideration of the case, the Human Rights Committee, acting in accordance with the provisions of Article 5, Paragraph 4, of the Optional Protocol to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights, held that the facts before it revealed violations by Ecuador of Articles 7, 10, Paragraphs 1 and 14, Paragraphs 3 (c) and (e) and 5, of the ICCPR.⁴² In regard to criminal charges, the ICCPR⁴³ provides for 'minimum guarantees, in full equality', inter-alia, in respect to prompt information of the nature and cause of the charge against the accused; adequate time and facilities for an accused to prepare his defense and to communicate with counsel of his own choosing; and the right to be tried timeously, without undue delay.

In the case of *Frank Robinson v. Jamaica*,⁴⁴ the Human Rights Committee held, the view that the facts submitted revealed, a violation of Article 14, Paragraphs 1 and 3 (d) of, the ICCPR. Considering that 'the refusal of the trial judge to order an adjournment to allow the author to have legal representation, when several adjournments had already been ordered when the prosecution's witnesses were unavailable or unready, raises issues of fairness and equality before the courts'.⁴⁵ Hence, all persons shall be equal before the law and, correlatively entitled to equal protection and access to all benefits, facilities, and privileges, guaranteed by the substantive laws of the State and in line with the best procedural practices for the administration of justice.

³⁶ *Tyonex (Nig.) Ltd. v. Pfizer Ltd.* [2020] 1 NWLR

³⁷ *Jaiyesimi v. Darlington* [2022] 9 NWLR

Alioke v Oye & Ors (2018) Vol. 286 LRCN

³⁸ CCPR/C/57/D/480/1991

³⁹ *José Luis García Fuenzalida v Ecuador* CCPR/C/57/D/480/1991 para 1

⁴⁰ *ibid* para 2.2

⁴¹ *ibid* para 3.6

⁴² *José Luis García Fuenzalida v Ecuador* CCPR/C/57/D/480/1991 para 10

⁴³ Article 14 (3) of the ICCPR

⁴⁴ Communication No. 233/1987

⁴⁵ *Frank Robinson v. Jamaica* Communication No. 233/1987 para 10.4

In the case of *William Eduardo Delgado v. Colombia*,⁴⁶ the Human Rights Committee affirmed the position of Article 25 (c) of the ICCPR,⁴⁷ that “every citizen shall have the right and opportunity, without unreasonable restrictions: To access on general terms of equality, the public service in his country.”

The case of *Peter Chiiko Bwalya v. Zambia*,⁴⁸ involved persecutory and prejudicial treatment that led to violations of Articles 9 (1) and (3), 12, 19 (1), 25 (a), and 26 of the International Court of Civil Rights.⁴⁹ The author was a politician who ran for a parliamentary seat in the Constituency of Chifubu, Zambia, in 1983. He alleged that the state authorities sabotaged his political rights. However, ‘the authorities’ action apparently helped to increase his popularity among the poorer strata of the local population, as the author was committed to changing the Government’s policy toward, in particular, the homeless and the unemployed.’⁵⁰ Nevertheless, as a consequence of his political activism, he was subjected to other acts of persecution by the State, including threats, intimidation, dismissal from employment in 1986, expulsion from a family property by the Ndola City Council, the indefinite suspension of his father’s pension, and other forms of hardship and harassment, which caused him to migrate ‘to Namibia, where other Zambian citizens had settled. Upon his return to Zambia, however, he was arrested and placed in custody.’⁵¹ The author’s ‘alleged discrimination, denial of employment, refusal of a passport’, the alleged ‘conspiracy to overthrow the Government’, arrests, detentions, and other prejudicial actions of the state were a consequence of his political affiliations and ideology, which was considered ‘illegal under the terms of the country’s one-party Constitution’.⁵² The case of *Peter Chiiko Bwalya v. Zambia*,⁵³ exemplifies how political aims can be applied as a basis for prejudicial treatment and breaches of treaty and statutory provisions that guarantee the equal protection of all persons’ rights. Mara recognized the possibility of such abusive practices in the context of the manipulation of symbolic power,⁵⁴ as well as Burns Weston and others who proscribe systemic and institutionalized acts of corruption.⁵⁵

3. Distributive equality

Distributive equality connotes the right of the citizenry to benefit from the equal distribution of public goods or opportunities. Article 22(1) of the African Charter on Human and Peoples Rights, provides that “All peoples shall

⁴⁶ Communication No. 195/1985

⁴⁷ *William Eduardo Delgado v. Colombia* Communication No. 195/1985 para 6

⁴⁸ Communication No. 314/1988

⁴⁹ *Peter Chiiko Bwalya v. Zambia* Communication No. 314/1988 para 7

⁵⁰ *ibid* para 2.2

⁵¹ *Peter Chiiko Bwalya v. Zambia* Communication No. 314/1988 paras 2.1 and 2.2

⁵² “The author states that, as a political activist and former prisoner of conscience, he has been placed under strict surveillance by the authorities and that he continues to be subjected to restrictions on his freedom of movement”. He claims that he has been denied a passport and any means of making a decent living.

ibid paras 2.3, 2.4, 3.2, and 33

⁵³ Communication No. 314/1988

⁵⁴ L Mara, ‘The Modern State and the primitive accumulation of symbolic power. *American Journal of Sociology*, 110(6), 1652

⁵⁵ BH Weston, *Human Rights* [1984] 6(3): *Human Rights Quarterly* 261

JM Mbaku, ‘International Law and the fight against bureaucratic corruption in Africa’ [2016] Vol. 33(3) *Arizona Journal of International and Comparative Law*, 33(3), 681.

S Asongu, ‘Fighting Corruption in Africa: Do Existing Corruption-Control Levels Matter?’ [2013] Vol. 21(1) *International Journal of Development* 39

have the right to their economic, social and cultural development with due regard to their freedom and identity and in the equal enjoyment of the common heritage of mankind.”⁵⁶

4. Verification of the right to equality through legislation and administrative decisions

In relation to the ‘verification theory of meaning’, verificationist have alluded to the act and the possibility of creating rules by virtue of ‘justified assertion.’⁵⁷ Such assertions can be given legal value and legitimacy through the exercise of legislative authority through statutory enactments or administrative decisions or policies that verify enforceability and, provide a legal basis for claims and adjudication.⁵⁸

The verification theory shares a strong affinity with positivism.⁵⁹ Thus, in legalistic terms, positive laws verify equality standards.⁶⁰ For instance, Article 3 of the African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act,⁶¹ provides that “every individual shall be equal before the law’, and ‘shall be entitled to equal protection” by the law.

According to Schlick, “to understand a proposition we must be able to indicate those particular circumstances that would make it true,” and vice versa.⁶² On that account, the certainty of standards is systemically afforded to the State by virtue of positive laws, which verify the “truth or falsity of propositions,”⁶³ as exemplified in the Canadian Supreme Court’s judgment that a constitutional obligation is a duty of the government, whose execution cannot be objected to.⁶⁴ Legislation is also consistent with Burke’s verification theory in the sense that laws ipso facto verify the validity or enforceability of provisions stated therein.⁶⁵ For example, Article 21(2) of the Universal Declaration of Human Rights,⁶⁶ verifies the fact that “everyone has the right to equal access to public service in his country.”

The case of *Grant Tadman et al. v Canada*,⁶⁷ was based on Section 93 of the Constitution Act, 1867, which obliged the State to fund Roman Catholic schools in the province of Ontario.⁶⁸ The province of Ontario operated a separate school funding system in line, with the 1867 Constitution of Canada, which was implemented for the

⁵⁶ African Charter on Human and Peoples’ Rights (Ratification and Enforcement) Act Chapter A9 (Chapter 10 LFN 1990) (No 2 of 1983) Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 1990

WTO, ‘Exploring the links between subsidies, trade and the WTO’ *World Trade Report*, 2006, xxii.

⁵⁷ D. Holdcroft, ‘Schlick and the Verification Theory of Meaning’ *Revue Internationale de Philosophie*, vol. 144, no. 145 (1/2) (1983), 47.

⁵⁸ *ibid*

⁵⁹ ‘n 57’ 48

⁶⁰ For example, the Nigerian Constitution obliges the legislative arm to make laws for “the peace order and good government of the Federation.”

Section 4 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, 1999 (as amended)

⁶¹ Chapter A9 (Chapter 10 LFN 1990) (No. 2 of 1983) Laws of the Federation of Nigeria 1990

⁶² ‘n 57’ 49

⁶³ *ibid*

⁶⁴ *Grant Tadman et al. v Canada* CCPR/C/67/D/816/1998 para 2.11

⁶⁵ Burke, T. E. “Self-Verification.” No. 112 (1971): 69-75. *Hermathena* 69

⁶⁶ Adopted and proclaimed by the General Assembly resolution 217 A (III) of December 10, 1948

⁶⁷ CCPR/C/67/D/816/1998

⁶⁸ *Grant Tadman et al. v Canada* CCPR/C/67/D/816/1998 para 1.2

benefit of 17% of the state's population, who were Roman Catholics.⁶⁹ The Constitutional basis of the separate funding system was, Section 93 of the Constitution Act, 1867, which grants each province in Canada exclusive jurisdiction to enact laws regarding education. The Education Act entitles separate schools to full public funding.⁷⁰ However, 'the issue of public funding for non-Catholic religious schools in Ontario has been the subject of domestic litigation since 1978'⁷¹. The objectivity of the State's policy initiative to fund Catholic schools and, its alleged inconsistency with the principle of equality of opportunity were questioned, considering that the benefits of the separate funding system did not extend to all citizens. This was also in line with the amended 1982 Constitution of Canada, which includes 'a Charter of Rights and Freedoms which contained an equality provision'.⁷²

On June 25, 1987, the Bill 30 case, the Supreme Court of Canada upheld the constitutionality of the legislation that extended full funding to Roman Catholic schools.⁷³ [...] On appeal, the Supreme Court of Canada, by a judgment of 21 November 1996 [...] found that the funding of Roman Catholic separate schools could not give rise to an infringement of the Charter because the province of Ontario was constitutionally obligated to provide such funding.⁷⁴

Thus, guaranteeing an equal right for all Catholic students to benefit from the separate funding policy.⁷⁵ Regarding the verification value of executive or administrative decisions and policies, a noteworthy example is the case of *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina*,⁷⁶ involving an Argentinean citizen who, merited the sixth position on the official roster as, the result of an open competitive examination for vacant judicial positions. After the first four positions were allotted, other vacancies were approved in chambers no. I, III, and, IV of the Rosario Civil and Commercial Court of Appeal.⁷⁷ The official roster was designated as valid for 18 months after the legislature approved it.⁷⁸ Consequently, the executive branch was expected to adhere to the hierarchy in, case of vacancies within the validity period.⁷⁹ On that account, in view of the vacancy in chamber no. III, the author submitted a written application to the Minister of Justice and Human Rights and to the Provincial Governor, stating that he should be appointed to fill the vacant office that arose in chamber no. III, on the merit of his sixth place on the official roster, in accordance with article 26 of Decree No. 854/16.⁸⁰ Thus, urging the State to strictly adhere to the examiners' roster rankings.

Irrespective of the author's application, 'the Governor had sent the appointment dossier for the new member of chamber no. III of the Civil and Commercial Court of Appeal to the legislature, having selected the candidate in

⁶⁹ *ibid* para 2.2

⁷⁰ *Grant Tadman et al. v Canada* CCPR/C/67/D/816/1998 para 2.3

⁷¹ *ibid* para 2.6

⁷² *ibid* para 2.7

⁷³ *ibid* para 2.8

⁷⁴ *ibid* para 2.11

⁷⁵ *ibid*

⁷⁶ E/C.12/68/D/149/2019

⁷⁷ *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina* E/C.12/68/D/149/2019 para 2.2

⁷⁸ *ibid* para 2.3

⁷⁹ *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina* E/C.12/68/D/149/2019 para 2.4

⁸⁰ *ibid*

ninth position'.⁸¹ The author further reported that the executive branch failed to adhere to the rankings in the nine most recent vacancies for appointment to chambers of the Civil and Commercial Courts of Appeal in the cities of Santa Fe de la Vera Cruz and Rosario.⁸² Consequently, the author filed an application for reconsideration in 2017, as well as an administrative injunction against the Governor's decision to discretionally appoint other candidates without recourse to the results of the competitive examinations.⁸³ He claimed that the executive's nominations were arbitrary, unlawful, non-transparent, not based on objective justifications, a closed selection process, and reflected unequal treatment.⁸⁴ Thus, "justifying a review to ensure compliance with the Constitution and the law."⁸⁵ The applicant also requested that the appointment dossier submitted to the legislature be provisionally halted pending the reconsideration suggested by his application.⁸⁶

In 2017, an interview convened by the Bicameral Commission on Agreements, in 2017, it was reported that 'the analysis carried out during the selection process is "merely political and that the Governor has the power to select whoever he wants."⁸⁷ Consequently, the author appealed to the Commission to uphold 'the right of access to public office on equal terms, without discrimination' and the public sector's obligation to 'act honestly and in good faith, in the interests of transparency in the public sector'.⁸⁸ Nonetheless, the State confirmed the judicial appointments. The author also alluded to the fact that 'the State party's case law consistently holds that the appointment of judges is a non-justiciable political matter'.⁸⁹

The competing issues in the case of *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina*,⁹⁰ were the right to equality of opportunity in the context of a hierarchy obtained from a competency-based assessment process and, the state's political prerogative to make subjective appointments largely based on political considerations. Based on the verdict of the court, in such scenarios, emphasis is placed on due process and appointments made either in line with the meritorious basis of qualifications founded on efficiency considerations or, the political discretion of executives based on the dictates of constitutional law. The latter is related to John Searle's concept of 'status functions', which affirms the state's authority to make appointments, either based on political or administrative discretion.⁹¹ Thus, when appointed, such citizens have a verified right to execute designated functions based on offices given to them by the state, in line with statutory defined procedures, or legitimate administrative appointments. Consequently, it affords all office holders an equal right to execute functions and benefit from the privileges accrued to their offices.

⁸¹ *ibid*

⁸² *ibid*

⁸³ *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina* E/C.12/68/D/149/2019 para 2.5

⁸⁴ *ibid*

⁸⁵ *ibid*

⁸⁶ *ibid*

⁸⁷ *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina* E/C.12/68/D/149/2019 para 2.6

⁸⁸ *ibid*

⁸⁹ *ibid* para 2.9

⁹⁰ E/C.12/68/D/149/2019

⁹¹ Saftescu-Jescu, 'A central problem of contemporary philosophy: Institutional facts. John Searle's point of view' [2013] Vol. 17 *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 149

J. Searle, *Making the social world. The Structure of Human Civilization* (Oxford University Press, 2010) 4, 98, 74, 49, 61, 102

5. Applying qualifications as a standard of equality

Qualifications are defined as conditions or official requirements that must be met before a right is acquired.⁹² Thus, qualified equality standards are created when the right to equality is subject to, or predicated on specific qualifications. For instance, it is a commonsensical fact that all certified doctors have an equal right to practice medicine and that a Call to Bar certificate affords all legal practitioners an equal right to practice law in Nigeria. Similarly, qualification standards are applicable to all professional fields and technical industries as a means of verifying the quality of labor. Using qualification as a standard of equality can also involve “narrowing the range of potential contractors” on the basis of efficiency considerations for the benefit of those who hold specific certifications or professional qualifications, with the aim of ensuring that ‘only capable contractors will obtain awards.’⁹³ The application of qualification standards is recommended based on the rationale that only qualified persons can effectively and efficiently discharge functions.⁹⁴ Various forms of training and levels of education are prerequisites for enhancing the ability of individuals to function efficaciously in specific fields of interest.⁹⁵ Thus, qualification standards can afford equality of opportunity, solely to qualified persons.

The case of *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina*,⁹⁶ involved an Argentinian citizen who claimed that the State violated his rights, guaranteed by Article 7(c) of the International Covenant on Economic, Social and Cultural Rights (ICESCR),⁹⁷ in the context of employment rights, specifically in regard to equality of opportunity and the right to be promoted without the hindrance of prejudicial considerations, except reasonable criteria concerning “seniority and competence.”⁹⁸ The author held a position in the judiciary, as a judge in the provincial court system of the city of Rosario, in the Province of Santa Fe, since March 8, 2012.⁹⁹ In view of the vacancies in Rosario’s Civil and Commercial Court of Appeal, which was superior to his current position, he participated in an open competitive examination organized by the Council of the Judiciary for the appointment of judges.¹⁰⁰ Subsequently, face-to-face interviews were conducted in 2016.¹⁰¹ Although the author “far exceeded the qualification criteria,” he was hierarchically positioned at number six on the official roster.¹⁰² Consequently, the four vacant positions were given to those with higher positions on the roster.¹⁰³ Regardless of the result, all the open competitive examination candidates were given an equal opportunity to participate, based on their judicial qualifications.

⁹² Oxford Languages, Qualification <<https://g.co/kgs/asPbNi7>> accessed 25 June 2025

⁹³ RE Lieblich, Robert, ‘Bidder Pre-Qualification: Theory in Search of Practice’ [1972] Vol. 5(1) *Public Contract Law Journal* 32

⁹⁴ BA Kumar, ‘Question of Minimum Educational Qualification for People’s Representatives’ [2009] Vol. 70(3) *The Indian Journal of Political Science*, 70(3), 873.

⁹⁵ *ibid*

⁹⁶ E/C.12/68/D/149/2019

⁹⁷ Adopted and opened for signature, ratification, and accession by resolution 2200 A (XXI) of the General Assembly of December 16, 1966

⁹⁸ *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina* E/C.12/68/D/149/2019 para 1.1

Section 7(c) of the ICESCR

⁹⁹ *ibid* para 2.1

¹⁰⁰ *ibid*

¹⁰¹ *ibid*

¹⁰² *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina* E/C.12/68/D/149/2019 para 2.2

¹⁰³ *ibid*

Conclusion

Articles 19 and 22 of the ACHPR recognize the right to equality. The Constitution vests legislative and administrative authority in the executive and legislative arm of the government.¹⁰⁴ Thus, the legislative arm of the state verifies sectionalized/categorized equality rights. For instance, Section 93 of the Constitution Act, 1867, which is enforced in Canada, guarantees an equal right to state funding for all students of Roman Catholic schools in the province of Ontario.¹⁰⁵ That is the basis of the view that standards of equality are verified through the identification of a common feature among a target population or group, and verifying the commonality of such a feature by virtue of a legislative or administrative action that vests common benefits or responsibility to members of the selected class – For example, students in the context of Section 93 of the Constitution Act, 1867.

Consequently, the violation of legally recognized equality standards leads to discriminatory practices. Thus, the principle of equality is predicated on a common standard that is antithetical to differences. Nonetheless, in practice, such common standards are expected to be based on reasonable and objective criteria, as opposed to discriminatory considerations.¹⁰⁶ Standards of equality can also be determined based on professional qualifications or efficiency considerations that limit the exercise of rights and concomitant benefits solely to qualified persons.¹⁰⁷ Nevertheless, due to inefficiencies, inefficacies, and systemic flaws, various economic, administrative, and political factors undermine the right to equality, especially in systemically corrupt countries.¹⁰⁸

¹⁰⁴ Sections 4 and 5 of the 1999 Constitution of the Federal Republic of Nigeria, (as amended)

¹⁰⁵ 'n 102' para 1.2

¹⁰⁶ *Arieh Hollis Waldman v Canada* CCPR/C/67/D/694/1996 para 10.6

¹⁰⁷ *Luciano Daniel Juárez v. Argentina* E/C.12/68/D/149/2019 para 1.1

¹⁰⁸ *Peter Chiiko Bwalya v. Zambia* Communication No. 314/1988